

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_d_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:48:57 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	26.68	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.4071	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_d_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:48:57 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	11.56	μm	
Min:	-8.403	μm	
Max:	3.154	μm	
Size:	283867	digits	
Spacing:	0.04071	nm	
NM-points ratio:	7.424 % (668168 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:48:57 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	11.56	μm	
Size:	283867	digits	
Spacing:	0.04071	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.362	μm	
Ssk	-1.872		
Sku	9.831		
Sp	3.145	μm	
Sv	8.411	μm	
Sz	11.56	μm	
Sa	0.8548	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	3.047	%	
Smc	1.385	μm	
Sxp	4.039	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	17.12	μm	
Str	0.7364		
Std	101.0	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.3034		
Sdr	3.681	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.05899	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.444	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.05899	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.6613	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	1.156	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2881	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	7.764	µm
Mean depth of furrows	1.301	µm
Mean density of furrows	3791	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	45.01	°
Second direction	180.0	°
Third direction	89.99	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	77.94	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

